
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE CHANGE OF THE STRENGTHENING ZONE ON CORRODED STEEL SPECIMENS

Antonio Shopov

Department “Strength of Materials”, Technical University of Sofia – 8, “Kliment Ohridski” blvd., Sofia, 1000, Bulgaria, European Union

Borislav Bonev

Department “Microelectronics”, Technical University of Sofia – 8, “Kliment Ohridski” blvd., Sofia, 1000, Bulgaria, European Union

ABSTRACT

The presence of the strengthening zone in the stress-strain diagram is explained by the fact that the sliding of each individual crystal in the steel cannot grow indefinitely. Corrosion have a negative influence on the steel element.

We have made an experiment to determine if there is a change in the zone of strengthening. For this purpose, we used classic S355JR structural steel subjected to electrochemical corrosion. We split the strengthening zone into 8 equal parts and took the values from the diagram. We processed them using the stochastic method. We have come to the conclusion that corrosion indicates a significant impact on this area by making the structure of the polycrystalline steel grid is transforming.

Key words: strengthening zone, corrosion, electrochemical accelerated corrosion method, remove corrosion product.

Cite this Article: Antonio Shopov and Borislav Bonev, Experimental Study of the Change of the Strengthening Zone on Corroded Steel Specimens, *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)* 10(1), 2019, pp. 2285–2293. <http://www.iaeme.com/IJCIET/issues.asp?JType=IJCIET&VType=10&IType=1>

1. INTRODUCTION

A large number of responsible structures with varied applications are subjected to both corrosion and mechanical stresses. Under these conditions, the strength and deformation characteristics of the steel are deteriorated. From a safety point of view, the construction solutions should be such that the load-bearing structure and the most responsible structural elements of the buildings will not be destroyed during the lifetime and in the event of an accident such as fire, earthquakes, etc. One of the challenges faced by modern construction is to increase the reliability of structural elements subjected to corrosion by simultaneously reducing their metal-strength, so corrosion studies are always up to date. There are many steel structures in which corrosion is clearly expressed (at an advanced stage) [2]. Some

researchers [1] find that the mechanism for determining mechanical properties for corrosion and stress corrosion is a complex process that depends on factors such as: energy accumulation, environmental impact, action of sulphate-reducing bacteria, electrochemical and destructive processes in a structural layer. Corrosion has been found to cause significant changes in the structure of steel as a [1-2, 15], but from a practical point of view how to change its dependence is not yet clear. It is known that corrosion also causes a negative influence on the spring constants [3]. There are many studies in the field of change of mechanical properties in corroded steel elements [1-2, 4-12, 15-16]. In the stress-strain diagram, there is a strengthening zone characterized by the corresponding structural steel grid and its tensile strength falls into its area. In the strengthening zone it is established that additional load bearing capacity was found to be relatively small, with the main reason for this being the altered structure of the plastic deformation. It is not fully established that the corrosion influence indicates a significant impact on this area [15] by making the corresponding transformation, reducing the strength marginally and directly affecting the structure of the polycrystalline steel grid by transforming steel in a brittle material. If corrosion changes mechanical properties and / or strength, it will also change the area of strengthening. The ability to determine the tensile strength of corroded steel load-bearing elements is also essential in terms of their re-use and / or residual resource exploitation [2] (Figure 1). The present study aims to determine whether there is a change in the strengthening zone of corroded steel elements.

Figure 1 Corroded steel elements in structure, whose residual resource exploitation should be determined

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The acceleration of the corrosion process is accomplished by using an external source of direct current and anodic dissolution of the steel [16]. The test sample is connected to the positive pole of the source (anode) and the negative is connected to a stainless-steel plate or other metal inert (cathode) [16]. A fixed current is applied for a given amount of time in order to achieve a certain degree of corrosion [16]. For the purpose of the study, we use a self-developed system for accelerated corrosion based on the galvanostatic electrochemical method. More details about the system are given in [16]. The test specimens are 25 pieces, divided into 3 groups of 8 pieces. One specimen will be corroded, but will not be tested (reserves as a control specimen). They are grouped by time duration of the corrosion treatment - 7, 12 and 18 days respectively for group A, B and C.

We have chosen a current of 400 mA for each test specimen, where the loss of mass for 24 hours determined by the Faraday formula is [13, 15-16]:

$$\eta[\%] = \frac{100 \times M \times I \times t}{W \times z \times F} = \frac{100 \times 56 \times 0.4 \times 24 \times 60 \times 60}{375 \times 2.5 \times 96484} = 2,14 \%, \quad (1)$$

where $M = 56$ g/mol is the atomic mass of the ferric ion, I [A] – electric current through the test specimen, t [s] – time duration of the treatment, W [g] is the weight of the steel specimen before corrosion treatment, z is the valence of the ferric ion ($z = 2,5$ is the average value for Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions of the corrosion products), $F = 96484$ C/mol is the Faraday constant.

We can determine the expectation loss of weight by using the result from Equation 1 for the three groups of specimens. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Expectation loss of weight for the three groups of specimens

	group A	group B	group C
days in corrosion	7	12	18
expectation loss of weight [g]	55	95	140

The system for accelerated corrosion consists of 50 adjustable current stabilizers. The current of each current stabilizer can be adjusted within the range of 16-200 mA [16]. In current case (400 mA), we can connect in parallel two current stabilizers, adjusted to maximum possible current (200 mA). With this connection, the current of the both current stabilizers are summed. Block diagram of the used in the present study configuration of the accelerated corrosion system is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Block diagram of the configuration of the accelerated corrosion system

Figure 3 Photograph of the current stabilizers before connection to the test specimens

Photograph of the current stabilizers before connection to the test specimens is shown in Figure 3. We use 2 modules of the system. Each module consists 25 adjustable current stabilizers. Block diagram and photograph of the experimental setup are shown in Figure 4. The experimental setup includes container with corrosive solution (5 % NaCl water solution), current stabilizers and digital multimeter. Each test specimen is connected to two parallel-

connected current stabilizers. The digital multimeter is used for monitoring of the working state of the system.

Figure 4 (a) Block scheme of the experimental setup; (b) Photograph of the experimental setup

The test specimens are placed in a self-developed special holder, which provides the necessary spacing between them. We use the holder in previous research [13, 15-16]. Furthermore, by using the holder greatly facilitates the process of removing the test pieces, measurements, and return back into the solution. The photograph of the holder with test specimens' group marked is shown in Figure 5. Weight measurements before corrosion treatment and after corrosion treatment and corrosion products removal are performed with precision balance [16] KERN model PNJ 600-3M with readability 0.001 g. Moments of these measurements are shown in Figure 6a and Figure 6b

Figure 5 Photograph of the test specimens' holder with marked groups

Figure 6 (a) Weight measurement of the test specimens before corrosion treatment; (b) Weight measurement of the test specimens after corrosion treatment and corrosion products removal

3. MATERIAL AND STEEL SPECIMEN

3.1. Steel specimen

We prefer to using a steel specimen which parallel length is a 15d [13, 15-16], Dimension and photos of our steel specimen is show on Figure 7a and Figure 7b.

Figure 7 (a) Dimensions of the steel specimen [13, 15-16]; (b) Photograph of the steel specimen

3.2. Material

We prefer to used in our study a structural steel S355JR, as we do [13, 15-16]. Our steel specimens have a chemical composition after a metal analysis for the determination of the chemical composition with Spector device “Spectrotest – TXC02; S/N 4S0007; analyzer: Fe-01MO; standard sample: RH 31/12, S3-2; type of probe: SL75060798”, is given on table 1 [16].

Table 2. Chemical composition on our steel specimens [16]

Chemical composition, [%]							
C	Si	Mn	P	S	Ni	Cu	Cr
0.23	0.52	1.554	0.03	0.04	0.27	0.53	0.27

We used a classic stress-strain curve (Fig. 8) on S355JR steel [15] and we split the strengthening zone into 8 equal parts (Fig.9) and took the values (stress and strain) from the stress-strain diagram, which is interest for us.

Figure 8 (a) Classic stress-strain curve; (b) Strengthening zone in stress-strain curve

Figure 9 (a) Strengthening zone divided on 8 parts; (b) mesh of strengthening zone

4. RESULTS

We used a universal testing machine MESSPHYSIK model BETA200-7/6x14 for tensile test our steel specimens and we tensile tested [13, 15-16] them according standard ISO 6892-1:2016. We remove corrosion products (rust) from steel specimens according ISO 9226 (Annex A) in hydrochloric acid - 10 min, in solution of 500 ml hydrochloric acid with 1000 ml distilled water and 3.5g hexamethylenetetramine on temperature 20°C [13, 15-16] – Figure 10. From our 25 steel specimens, we tested 24 samples and one of them is a control specimen (according to the rules of laboratory test procedure). We use the stochastic method to process the obtained empirical data [13, 15-16], as these are random variables [14].

Figure 10 (a) Moment of tensile test of the steel specimen with corrosion (b) Principle scheme of remove of the corrosion products from steel specimen [16] (c) Moment of removing corrosion products from steel specimen

Table 2 Results of strain values

№ of point in mesh	stochastic result			average results		
	group A (%)	group B (%)	group C (%)	group A (%)	group B (%)	group C (%)
0	0.65257	0.35500	0.34023	0.63574	0.31385	0.34915
1	0.77220	0.44533	0.43870	0.78915	0.41606	0.41144
2	0.89806	0.52733	0.44941	0.87255	0.47828	0.46697
3	1.04667	0.60667	0.49477	1.01960	0.53049	0.53249
4	1.07650	0.67600	0.54756	1.11936	0.59270	0.58802
5	1.23647	0.74933	0.60780	1.23277	0.65491	0.65354
6	1.33951	0.84133	0.63387	1.34617	0.71713	0.69907
7	1.49668	0.93247	0.69199	1.46958	0.78934	0.77459
8	1.61067	1.04000	0.77022	1.53298	0.84155	0.81012

Table 3 Results of stress values

№ of point in mesh	stochastic result			average results		
	group A (MPa)	group B (MPa)	group C (MPa)	group A (MPa)	group B (MPa)	group C (MPa)
0	364.420	359.912	368.841	366.862	351.917	377.949
1	388.410	391.115	414.919	386.218	363.464	392.721
2	406.417	396.351	427.916	401.236	379.796	404.909
3	412.479	417.921	434.920	415.937	388.332	411.261
4	424.589	426.232	439.918	426.115	404.564	422.339
5	432.601	433.862	441.918	433.230	410.170	429.710
6	443.916	440.455	445.522	438.657	418.782	435.608
7	449.913	443.937	448.922	441.462	421.663	440.923
8	450.913	447.759	451.922	444.267	426.673	447.968

Table 4 Results of weights

№ of steel specimen in group	group A		group B		group C	
	initially weight	final weight	initially weight	final weight	initially weight	final weight
	(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)
1	389.186	319.874	364.055	269.040	367.830	223.263
2	385.645	318.705	371.059	274.371	373.177	203.514
3	380.845	326.442	364.307	271.290	356.109	208.285
4	390.766	327.218	360.351	265.070	370.153	219.129
5	384.358	315.342	361.351	267.864	350.705	207.352
6	387.051	318.439	350.818	258.815	375.068	234.937
7	387.295	320.102	371.112	276.390	364.926	208.429
8	390.649	335.387	363.537	268.251	363.684	219.682

Figure 11 Results from experiment (group A)

Figure 12 Results from experiment (group B)

Figure 13 Results from experiment (group C)

5. CONCLUSIONS

When corrosion is at an early stage of development in a steel element, its impact on the strengthening zone is negligible or rather a reduction in ductility in this zone but does not reduce strength. At the next moment of development of the corrosion process, it is established (by the experiment) that there is a clear discrepancy between the non-corroded element and the corroded one. This fact gives us reason to believe that structural changes have occurred within the material, and the crystal lattice of steel has begun to change. When corrosion is at an advanced stage, the strengthening zone has already passed into a brittle material, this part of the diagram has no contact with the diagram of non-corrosive material, the loss of ductility is susceptible, and there are prerequisites for the brittleness of the material, resulting in the conclusion that there is an irreversible structural change in the crystal lattice of the steel.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research received is funding by “Hyosel” Ltd., Sofia, Bulgaria.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ganey, R. and Godiniachki, G. Steel corpuses destroying from tiredness and stress corrosion. Proceedings of the 5th Scientific Conference Fire and emergency safety 2009, Sofia, Bulgaria, 2009, pp. 190-192.
- [2] Ivanova, B., Ganey, R. and Drdacky, M. Historical and condition survey of the St.Stefan Bulgarain metal church in Istanbul. *International Journal of Architectural Heritage*, 7(6), 2013, pp. 693-714.
- [3] Shopov, A., Bonev, B. and Brayonov, N. Change of spring constant for springs with corrosion. Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Road and Rail Infrastructure CETRA 2018, Zadar, Croatia, 2018, pp. 291-297.
- [4] Chen, G., Hadi, M., Gao, D. and Zhao, L. Experimental study on the properties of corroded steel fibres. *Construction and Building Materials*, 79, 2015, pp. 165-172.
- [5] Ponjayuthi, D. and Vinodh, K. Effect of corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel reinforcement, *IJCRR*, 8(12), 2016, pp. 14-20.
- [6] Chen, H., Zhang, J., Yang, J. and Ye, F. Experimental investigation into corrosion effect on mechanical properties of high strength steel bars under dynamic loadings. *International Journal of Corrosion*, 2018, article number 7169681.
- [7] Zhao, Z. and Fu, L. The probability distribution of pitting for accelerated corrosion reinforcement. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 9, 2018, article number e00193.
- [8] Wu, X., Li, L., Li, H., Li, B. and Ling, Z. Effect of strain level on corrosion of stainless steel bar. *Construction and Building Materials*, 163, 2018, pp. 189-199.

- [9] Kim, I., Dao, D., Jeong, Y., Huh, J. and Ahn, J. Effect of corrosion on the tension behavior of painted structural steel members. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 133, 2017, pp. 256-268.
- [10] Sheng, J. and Xia, J. Effect of simulated pitting corrosion on the tensile properties of steel. *Construction and Building Materials*, 131, 2017, pp. 90-100.
- [11] Qin, G., Xu, S., Yao, D., Zhang, Z. Study on the degradation of mechanical properties of corroded steel plates based on surface topography. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 125, 2016, pp. 205-217.
- [12] Chen, H., Zhang, J., Yang, J. and Ye, F. Experimental investigation into corrosion effect in mechanical properties of high strength steel bars under dynamic loading. *International Journal of Corrosion*, 2018, article number 7169681.
- [13] Shopov, A. and Bonev, B. Experimental study of zone of yield strength on corroded construction steel specimens for reuse. Proceedings of the 10th Anniversary International Scientific Conference Building defects 2018, Ceske Budejovice, Czech Republic, 2018, pp.161-167.
- [14] Shopov, A. Stochastic way for calculation of strength on construction steel with corrosion. Proceedings of the XVIII Anniversary International Scientific Conference by Construction and Architecture VSU'2018, Sofia, Bulgaria, 2018, pp. 413-418.
- [15] Shopov, A. and Bonev, B. Ascertainment of the change of the ductility in corroded steel specimens by experiment. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 10(1), 2019, pp. 1551-1560.
- [16] Shopov, A. and Bonev, B. Change of young's module on steel specimens with corrosion by experiment, *International Journal of Modeling and Optimization* (in press).
- [17] Nirwan Nasrullah, Herman Parung, Nur Ali and M. Isran Ramli, Study of Behavior Transition To User Moda Personal Transport Public Transport On The Way In The District Takalar, *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 8(6), 2017, pp. 1008–1015
- [18] Reji Kumar R and Sivapragash M, Corrosion Behaviour of Magnesium-Tricalcium Phosphate Composite in Simulated Body Fluid, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 8(7), 2017, pp. 345–351
- [19] F. Zulkiflia, M.I.N. Isa, A.Y. ElInhibition of Aluminium Alloy 5083 by Lawsonia Inermis In Tropical Seawater, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET)*2018, pp. 654–670
- [20] Nadir Mohamed Abdulreda, Corrosion Inhibition of Carbon Steel in NACL and HCL Solutions By Vitamin C, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology (IJARET)*, Volume 5, Issue 4, April (2014), pp. 38-45